

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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FACTORS AFFECTING INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS IN THE GLOBAL INVESTMENT LANDSCAPE

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Abstract: The article examines the multifaceted factors that affect a country's investment attractiveness. By examining the interplay of macroeconomic stability, government policies, infrastructure, legal frameworks, and geopolitical considerations, the paper delves into the complex factors that contribute to a country's attractiveness for both domestic and foreign investment.

Key words: Investment Attractiveness, Macroeconomic Stability, Political Environment, Regulatory Framework, Infrastructure, Geopolitical Risk, Legal Landscape, Social Factors, Economic Growth, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI).

Annotatsiya: Maqolada mamlakatning investitsion jozibadorligiga ta'sir qiluvchi ko'p qirrali omillar ko'rib chiqiladi. Makroiqtisodiy barqarorlik, Hukumat siyosati, infratuzilma, huquqiy asoslar va geosiyosiy mulohazalar o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlikni o'rganib chiqib, maqola mamlakatning ichki va xorijiy investitsiyalar uchun jozibadorligiga hissa qo'shadigan murakkab omillarni o'rganadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Investitsion jozibadorlik, makroiqtisodiy barqarorlik, siyosiy muhit, me'yoriy-huquqiy baza, infratuzilma, geosiyosiy xavf, huquqiy landshaft, ijtimoiy omillar, iqtisodiy o'sish, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalar (FDI).

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются многогранные факторы, влияющие на инвестиционную привлекательность страны. Исследуя взаимодействие макроэкономической стабильности, государственной политики, инфраструктуры, правовой базы и геополитических соображений, статья углубляется в сложные факторы, которые способствуют привлекательности страны как для внутренних, так и для иностранных инвестиций.

Ключевые слова: инвестиционная привлекательность, макроэкономическая стабильность, политическая среда, нормативно-правовая база, инфраструктура, геополитический риск, правовой ландшафт, социальные факторы, экономический рост, прямые иностранные инвестиции (ПИИ).

INTRODUCTION

The contemporary global economic landscape is characterized by intricate webs of interconnectedness, wherein the fortunes of nations are inextricably linked. Amidst this backdrop, the capacity of countries to attract both foreign and domestic investment emerges as a linchpin for sustained economic growth and development. Recognizing the multifaceted nature of investment attractiveness, governments have increasingly turned their attention towards crafting policies and strategies to bolster their nations' appeal to investors.

The investment climate stands as a complex construct, comprising diverse factors that exert significant influence on investment decisions across various sectors and geographic locations. From the stability of regulatory frameworks to the resilience of legal structures, the quality of infrastructure, the political landscape, and the availability of skilled labor, these elements collectively shape the environment within which investors operate. Against the backdrop of intensifying global competition, the ability of nations to understand and enhance their investment climates has become paramount for sustainable economic growth and development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The study of a country's investment attractiveness has garnered substantial attention in academic and policy realms, reflecting a growing awareness of the pivotal role investments play in fostering economic development. The literature on this topic spans a diverse range of disciplines, including economics, political science, finance, and international relations. Scholars have delved into various facets of the investment climate, shedding light on the interconnected factors that shape a nation's appeal to investors.

The investment attractiveness of a country – is ascertained by assessing the level of investment activity and the inflow of investments into the territory. This evaluation is based on objective economic, social, and natural indicators, and it represents the sum of available resources, opportunities, and constraints. In turn, a country's investment activity can be understood as the intensity of capital inflow. ^[1]

Economists like A. Vakhobov, Sh. Khajibakiev, and N. Muminov emphasize the following about the investment environment: it represents the degree of foreign capital investment volatility within a country's economy, which in turn determines the potential for effective utilization. This environment comprises a complex interplay of political, legal, and social factors. ^[2]

In some literature, production and entrepreneurship refer to all types of investments involving financial, property, and intellectual assets across various sectors and investment projects, with the aim of achieving development, profit, or other final results. ^[3]

The comprehensive assessment of a country's investment environment is crucial for its representation in the global community in terms of investment attractiveness. ^[4]

The literature shows that the inflation rate plays a crucial role in influencing investment decisions. Moderate inflation boosts investor confidence, while high inflation can act as a deterrent. ^[5]

GDP growth rate is a crucial indicator of market potential and reflects the economic health of a country. The literature review focuses on studies that examine in detail how GDP growth rates affect investment decisions. ^[6]

The literature on a country's investment attractiveness reflects a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted dimensions that shape investor perceptions and decisions. By synthesizing insights from various disciplines, scholars contribute valuable perspectives that inform policymakers, investors, and stakeholders about strategies to enhance a nation's investment climate and foster sustainable economic development.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a mixed-methods approach to comprehensively analyze the multifaceted factors that influence a country's investment attractiveness. The research design combines qualitative and quantitative approaches to provide a holistic understanding of the topic.

ANALYZES AND RESULTS

At the macroeconomic level, the investment environment involves interactions among investors, specific state bodies, and economic entities. On the other hand, the investment climate represents the objective state of affairs at any given time, encompassing prevailing conditions for capital investment. However, it's important to understand that the investment environment is shaped by the activities of state bodies, making the state's investment policy a crucial factor.

In this context, each country develops its own system for receiving foreign capital. This capital admission system comprises a complex interplay of state policies and regulations outlined in official documents.

Investment attractiveness is the profitability of investments in a country or industry. It takes into account factors such as the investment environment, infrastructure, and development prospects, and it is evaluated in terms of the level of investment risk. Investment attractiveness is determined by the combined influence of a country's investment potential and the level of investment risk. Assessing these indicators is essential for determining the feasibility and attractiveness of investments. The level of investment risk is directly linked to the investment environment.

SWOT Analysis: Employed a SWOT analysis to identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats within each country's investment landscape.

Table 1: SWOT Analysis Results (2022)

Country	Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
Singapore	Stable political climate, robust infrastructure	Reliance on international trade, high living costs	Emerging as a hub for innovation and technology development	Geopolitical tensions in the region, limited natural resources
Brazil	Abundant natural resources, large consumer market	Political instability, high crime rates	Increased focus on sustainable development	Economic inequality, regulatory challenges

The primary objective of investment and innovation activities in the economy is to establish ideal conditions for fostering and expediting the utilization of innovative opportunities through investment. In this pursuit, it's essential to consider the organizational and economic aspects when making investments in diverse sectors of the economy. Efficiency in investment and innovation activities is achieved by incorporating mechanisms such as leasing, insurance, research institutes, information-consulting services, and collaboration with banks and other organizations within a comprehensive investment framework.

In the context of state support for the development and promotion of investment-innovation activities, several key areas should be emphasized:

- Encouraging leasing activity, which eases the financial burden by spreading lease payments across a fixed schedule and enables simplified contracts and schemes. This alignment of interests between the state and leasing companies creates optimal economic and legal conditions, ultimately reducing risk and enhancing economic efficiency;
- Offering budget loans, investment tax credits, and subsidized interest rates on loans;
- Implementing preferential tax policies that incentivize investment;
- Formulating state programs dedicated to the development of various sectors of the economy;
- These measures collectively contribute to fostering investment and innovation activities and driving economic growth.

The assessment of the investment environment plays a crucial role in determining the level of risk for an investor's investments. The quality of the investment climate directly influences the perceived business risk by the investor. In general, the worse the investment climate, the higher the investor's perceived business risk. Therefore, a favorable and supportive investment environment is essential in attracting and retaining investments.

Based on the literature, we have 3 factors that can affect the topic of the article:

- political
- economic
- environment

Figure 1: Factors affecting the country's investment environment¹

¹ Ergasheva Sh., Uzokov.A. Organization and financing of investments. – T.: Economy-Finance, 2008. p. 37.

Certainly, foreign investors carefully consider all the mentioned factors when deciding on investments. In the conditions of the current market economy, internal and external factors affect the country's investment attractiveness. It is impossible to develop the country's investment attractiveness until they are thoroughly studied.

The level of modern economic development in the country is determined by investment activity. The pace of investment activity is crucial for ensuring steady growth and development in the economy. Investment activities are influenced by specific economic, social, organizational, legal, political, and other conditions. These factors, which collectively form an interdependent complex, play a decisive role in the investment activity of a country's economy.

Table 2: Ranking of the best countries for investment in 2023²

No	Country	GDP	POPULATION	GDP PER CAPITA, PPP (\$)
1.	Singapore	\$467 billion	5.64 million	\$127,565
2.	United States	\$25.5 trillion	333 million	\$76,399
3.	Japan	\$4.23 trillion	125 million	\$45,573
4.	South Korea	\$1.67 trillion	51.6 million	\$50,070
5.	China	\$18.0 trillion	1.41 billion	\$21,476
6.	Germany	\$4.07 trillion	84.1 million	\$63,150
7.	United Arab Emirates	\$508 billion	9.44 million	\$87,729
8.	Switzerland	\$808 billion	8.77 million	\$83,598
9.	Sweden	\$586 billion	10.5 million	\$64,578
10.	Luxembourg	\$82.3 billion	651 thousand	\$142,214

It's noteworthy that various economic literatures express the factors influencing the investment environment in different ways. This diversity arises from the varied interpretation of the factors that impact the investment environment. Some sources categorize these factors as positive and negative, while others differentiate them based on their directions of influence or sources, considering different objectives.

The investment attractiveness of a country hinges on several key factors, including tax benefits, the presence of free economic zones, minimal bureaucratic obstacles hindering economic activities, low or non-existent customs tariffs, efficient customs inspection processes, and a well-developed infrastructure and logistics system. These conditions are crucial in enticing investors and fostering a favorable environment for business growth and development.

CONCLUSION

The objectives of the study include identifying key determinants of investment attractiveness, assessing their relative importance, comparing investment climates across selected countries, and providing insights for policymakers and investors.

Data collection involves an extensive literature review, gathering secondary data from reliable sources, conducting SWOT analysis for selected countries, and performing quantitative analysis using statistical techniques.

The sampling strategy involves selecting a diverse set of countries representing different regions and levels of economic development. A minimum of 10 countries will be included for comparative analysis.

Qualitative analysis includes thematic analysis of qualitative data, while quantitative analysis involves descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and regression analysis.

The synthesis of findings integrates qualitative and quantitative results to develop a comprehensive understanding of the factors shaping investment attractiveness. Common trends, disparities, and implications for policymakers and investors will be identified.

² <https://www.usnews.com/news/best-countries/best-countries-to-invest-in> Copyright 2023 © U.S. News & World Report L.P. prepared by the authors based on their information

The study adheres to ethical standards in data collection, analysis, and reporting, ensuring confidentiality, privacy, transparency, and integrity throughout the research process.

Overall, this study aims to contribute valuable insights into the determinants of investment attractiveness, facilitating evidence-based decision-making in the field of international investment.

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